

Dissociation Constants of Diethyldithiocarbamic Acid in Water

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Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate has been previously investigated in our laboratories.^{1,4} It was concluded that the two P_k 's are 7.5 and 8.4 respectively, so that after successive approximation², the values are 7.8 ± 0.1 and 8.0 ± 0.1 ³ respectively. In this work ionic strength was neglected. In the present work the values of the dissociation constants are determined at various ionic concentrations and extrapolated to zero ionic concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present work, HCIO_4 was employed as it is the strongest acid and has minimum tendency towards complex formation. The ionic strength was made up by addition of NaClO_4 . As the mixture of solutions of NaDDC and HCIO_4 showed a gradual change in $p\text{H}$, the mixtures were kept in pyrex glass stoppered flasks for about 24 hours, and $p\text{H}$ of the solutions were subsequently measured. The flasks were kept at room temperature (about 30°) and $p\text{H}$ of the solution was noted with Leeds and Northrup $p\text{H}$ meter (catalogue no. 7666) equipped with glass and fibrous type saturated calomel electrodes. The $p\text{H}$ meter was standardized frequently with the buffer solutions of $p\text{H}$ 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2. NaDDC was of B.D.H. A.R. quality. All other chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade. Doubly distilled water was used throughout the investigation. The acid was standardized with at least two different bases. A stock solution of the requisite molarity (25 mM or 10mM) of NaDDC was prepared in NaClO_4 of different molarities. Similarly, HCIO_4 was prepared in the same molarity of NaClO_4 so as to maintain the ionic strength constant. 25 ml. of NaDDC solution was taken in a glass stoppered flask and different ml. of HCIO_4 was added. The $p\text{H}$ of different solutions were measured at 30° . The solutions of different ionic strengths were obtained by adding 0.04, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0M NaClO_4 . The values of pK_{D1} and pK_{D2} were determined as described previously¹.

DISCUSSION

In the present work, 25mM and 10mM NaDDC solutions were prepared in water and in 0.04, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0M NaClO_4 as a background electrolyte. In final calculations of the ionic strength, the molarity of NaDDC solution was taken into account, e.g., in the

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2. Rossotti and Rossotti, 'The determination of stability constants', 1st edition, 1961, McGraw Hill Book Co., N. Y. Chapter V.
3. Soni, Trivedi and Bhatt, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 85.
4. Soni, 'Ph. D. Thesis' submitted to the Gujarat University, 1965.

case of 25mM NaDDC solution the ionic strengths were 0.025, 0.125, 0.225, 0.525 and 1.025. The values of pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} obtained by reading the values of pH corresponding to $1\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ equivalents of acid added, were plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$. The extrapolated values at zero ionic strength turned out to be 7.5 and 8.0 respectively. As the difference between pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} is less than 0.8, it may be concluded that computation method, such as successive approximation method cannot be applied and pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} will be very nearly equal to 7.8 ± 0.1 .

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